

INVESTIGATION INTO THE EFFECTIVENESS OF A COLUMN CONFINEMENT WITH TEXTILE REINFORCED CONCRETE (TRC)

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to analyze the results of uniaxial compression tests conducted on textile-reinforced concrete (TRC) – confined reinforced concrete (RC) columns. The aim of this study is the investigation of various influences on the achievable strengthening effect. The impact of the ratio of textile reinforcement and concrete strength on ultimate strength increase is evaluated. Also, the influence of the concrete jacket on the overall increase in load-bearing capacity was investigated. The results show an increase in strength and deformation related to the unstrengthened reference columns. Also, a higher ductility of the reinforced columns could be achieved.

KEYWORDS

Concrete Columns; Textile reinforced concrete; Confinement; Experimental test; Stress-Strain

INTRODUCTION

Confinement with TRC

RC columns represent an important structural element of the entire static system. These are essential components for the transfer of vertical loads into the foundation. However, their cross-sections rarely have greater load-bearing reserves, so an increase in the original column load makes subsequent reinforcement unavoidable. With the restoration or an increase of the load-bearing capacity of the column, the total carrying capacity of the whole building can also be effectively upgraded. For the subsequent reinforcement of columns, the classic and established methods for reinforcement, for example, shotcrete is usually used. The additional layer thicknesses required to protect the reinforcement from corrosion result in significantly higher dead loads, which have to be taken into account in the structural analysis. Consequently, this type of reinforcement will not meet today's requirements for sustainability and resource efficiency, which means that innovative retrofitting methods such as carbon fiber reinforcement (CFRP) or TRC appear more promising.

In the case of reinforcement with CFRP, the carbon fiber mesh is bonded to the old concrete by an epoxy resin. This allows the load to be absorbed transversely to the direction of loading and impedes the transverse expansion of the column (Lam et al., 2003). Although the CFRP layers result in only small layer thicknesses, structural fire protection must be ensured by additional measures. Furthermore, the sensitivity to UV radiation, the inapplicability on wet surfaces, hazards for the manual worker, diffusion tightness, and high costs are also disadvantages of this material (Ombres, 2014).

These disadvantages were recognized and the development of TRC was pushed forward. TRC is an innovative building material that has been researched for over two decades now. While combining the advantages of shotcrete and CFRP, this composite material usually consists of a flat textile fabric reinforcement structure that is embedded in a fine-grained, high strength concrete (Figure 1) (Bournas et al., 2007). Advantageous features like a high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion, and fire resistance. On the one hand, the old concrete can be repassivated due to the additional concrete application. On the other hand the fire protection properties of the as-built component can be improved by the applied concrete jacket. A significant advantage is the corrosion resistance of the textile reinforcement material. The concrete cover required to ensure durability is no longer necessary, which both saves material and reduces the space required for the measure (Curbach et al., 2023).

Figure 1: Two-layer structure of TRC

Compared to classical reinforced concrete, much smaller thicknesses and thus lower dead loads with at the same time higher load-bearing capacity and lower material consumption can be achieved. For application as a reinforcement element, various materials can be considered. In addition to high tensile strength, a further high number of requirements are placed on the textiles depending on the place, purpose, and duration of use.

General basic requirements such as a high modulus of elasticity, sufficient elongation at break, low changes in properties under temperature stress, and sufficient resistance to media are prerequisites for use in an alkaline environment. Furthermore, additional properties with regard to bonding and deformation behavior must be complied with. From the wide range of requirements, fibers such as carbon, alkali-resistant (AR) glass, aramid, and PBO (Zylon) are suitable for the production of textile reinforcements. In a comparison of the various materials, carbon fibers can be highlighted. Carbon is characterized by very high strength and stiffness, as well as a low creep tendency, coupled with excellent creep and fatigue strengths. Due to the molecular composition carbon fibers can be used without any problems in the alkaline environment of concrete (Jesse, 2004). In contrast to glass fibers, no strength losses were observed when used as a reinforcing element in concrete components (Büttner, 2012).

Mode of action

In comparison to the established retrofitting methods such as shotcrete, where the increase in load-bearing capacity is achieved by the enlargement of the cross-section by adding concrete and steel reinforcement, the mode of action of a TRC confinement results from the transverse strain restraining effect of the textile reinforcement. The carbon fiber fabrics, which are usually applied unidirectionally, allow forces to be absorbed transversely to the direction of loading and thus impede the transverse strain of the loaded column (Toska et al., 2023).

Since the carbon fiber is wrapped around the component without prestress, there is initially a passive restraint. The mesh is only activated by a continuation of the crack growth, which results in a, for the cylindrical cross-sections constant transverse pressure σ_r (Figure 2). The resulting transverse pressure leads to a multi-axial stress state, which significantly increases both the load-bearing capacity and the maximum compression of the whole component (Colajanni et al., 2014).

Figure 2: Formation of a transverse pressure due to confinement

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Experimental Program

In order to investigate the (a) possible increase in ultimate load and (b) influence of the concrete compressive strength on the reinforcing effect (c) influence of the fine-grained concrete jacket on the overall increase in load-bearing capacity the main objectives of the experimental program were the ratio of textile reinforcement and concrete strength of the strengthening component. Therefore the experimental program, shown in Table 1 includes 24 steel-reinforced concrete cylindrical specimens, which are divided into two groups with different compressive strengths.

In order to simulate a component in need of rehabilitation in the existing structure the core concrete compressive strength of the first series (C20) was chosen to be low. From the literature (Gonzalez-Libreros et al., 2019), it is known that the core concrete compressive strength has a great influence on the confining pressure of the reinforcement system, which is why it was increased in the second series (C55) up to a target compressive strength class of C55 (Kaeseberg, 2020). Specimen with the Label 2L20 and 4L23 are equipped with 20 mm and 23 thick layers of fine-grained concrete in which two or four layers of carbon textile are embedded. The original goal was to place the four layers in 20 mm of fine concrete. However, due to disturbances during confining processing, this could not be exactly achieved, resulting in a total layer thickness of 23 mm for four layers. To further evaluate the influence of the fine-grained concrete coating on the achievable strengthening effect, three test specimens in each series with the label FC20 were coated with 20 mm fine-grained concrete without any embedded textil. Specimen R of each series represents the reference unconfined specimens consisting only of the steel reinforced core concrete.

All specimens have a diameter D of 200 mm and height H of 1000 mm and have been tested under a longitudinal force load.

Table 1: Experimental Program

Series	Specimen label	No. of spec.	H/D	Confinement	f_{c0} [N/mm ²]	$f_{cm,m}$ [N/mm ²]
C20	R	3	5	reference	27.67	-
	2L20	3	5	2 layers, 20 mm fine-grained concrete	30.76	94.96
	4L23	3	5	4 layers, 23 mm fine-grained concrete	28.14	96.71
	FC20	3	5	20 mm fine-grained concrete	28.72	92.53
C55	R	3	5	reference	60.72*	-
	2L20	3	5	2 layers, 20 mm fine-grained concrete	60.72*	81.64
	4L20	3	5	4 layers, 20 mm fine-grained concrete	60.72*	78,84
	FC20	3	5	20 mm fine-grained concrete	60.72*	85.03

* mean value determined on three cubes

Specimen Preparation

Each test series was cast out of the same recipe designed to obtain a cylindrical compressive strength (f_{c0}) of 20 MPa for Series C20 and 55 MPa for C55. The cement content was 240 kg/m³ in C20 and 330 kg/m³ in C55 while the water-cement ratio (w/c) was 0.75 in C20 and 0.48 in C55. The cement:sand:gravel proportions in the concrete mixtures were around 1:3.22:4.80 in C20 and 1:2.34:3.46 in C55 by weight and the maximum size of the coarse aggregate was 16 mm in both series.

With the aim to determine the mechanical properties of the concrete, three cylindrical specimens measuring 150 x 300 mm for each series were made out of the same batch and tested on the same day as the main specimens. The compressive strengths of the core f_{c0} and of the fine-grained concrete $f_{cm,m}$ are shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the specimens were provided with a steel reinforcement content of 2.36 cm²/m. Six rebars with a diameter of Ø12 mm as longitudinal reinforcement and every 10 cm

cross-sectional reinforcement out of $\varnothing 6$ mm curved rebars were used. The tensile strength of the steel rebars was 500 MPa and Young's modulus of 200 GPa. The concrete cover of all of the specimens was 15 mm.

Before any confinement works, the surface of the specimen needed to be prepared. A middle roughness of the surface of around 1 mm could be achieved by sandblasting the specimen until the aggregate with a diameter of > 4 mm was visible. Furthermore 24 hours before confining, the specimens were prewetted and covered with foil. The surface was wetted again and cleaned of dust 20 minutes before confining. To ensure uniform loading, all specimens were capped with fine-grained concrete.

Figure 3: Difference of the surfaces before and after sandblasting (left); capping process (right)

Confining Materials

The confining materials, which were used are regulated by the german general technical approval Z-31.10-182 (DIBt, 2021). It designates the use of the textile reinforcement TUDALIT-BZT1-TUDATEX, which is a bidirectional warped mesh impregnated with a film-forming dispersion based on Styrene-butadiene rubber. According to the approval, only the yarns in the warp direction with the red knitting thread (Figure 4) may be used for reinforcement. Important mechanical properties are summarized in Table 2. To prevent any fibre failure the minimum bending radius is 15 cm.

As a mortar matrix, the fine-grained concrete TF10 CARBOrefit® from Pagel GmbH is being used. This concrete has a maximum grain size of 1 mm and has been specially developed for the processing of carbon reinforcements in the hand lay-up or spray process. The concrete mixture, which is available as ready-mixed concrete, has a characteristic minimum compressive strength equal to 80 MPa. The compressive strengths $f_{cm,m}$ were measured using three prisms for each confined specimen and are shown in Table 1.

Figure 4: Structure of TRC carbon mesh

Table 2: Characteristics of the textile reinforcement TUDALIT-BZT2-V.FRAAS according to Z-31.10-182 (DIBt, 2021))

Properties of a coated carbon yarn	Properties in warp direction
Number of filaments per yarn	3200/3300 tex
Fiber cross-sectional area	
Textile	140 mm ² /m
Yarn	1.8 mm ²
Tensile strength	
Mean value	1980 MPa
Characteristic value	1890 MPa
Modulus of elasticity	
Mean value	170 GPa
Characteristic value	166 GPa
Ultimate strain	
Mean value	1.28 %
Characteristic value	1.24 %
Coating	Styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR) - Lefasol VLT-1

Instrumentation of the specimens

All 24 specimens were stored for more than 28 days under controlled temperature and humidity conditions (20 °C and 60 % relative humidity) until the testing. The wrapping started with the application of the first 5 mm layer of fine-grained concrete. After, the first ply of carbon mesh was applied and slightly pressed into the mortar. The textile was then wrapped around the specimens under slight tension, and the next layer of fine-grained concrete was applied in parallel (Figure 5 a)). These processes of wrapping and applying the fine-grained concrete were repeated until the required number of layers was achieved. As a concrete cover, a final 5 mm layer of fine-grained concrete was applied. By using additional stencils, uniform total layer thicknesses of 20 mm could be realized (Figure 5 b)). In addition, to prevent premature debonding failure of fibers, an overlap length of 50 cm was provided in the confined specimen. Furthermore, one layer of CFRP was applied to avoid a failure in the column head and foot (Figure 5 c)).

a)

b)

c)

Figure 5: a) wrapping process; b) uniform total layer thicknesses; c) test setup

Experimental setup

All tests were performed using a servo-hydraulic compression testing machine with a maximum load-carrying capacity of 6000 kN. The tests were done in deformation-controlled mode, primarily to allow accurate analysis of the processes of load transfer to the reinforcing layer and failure. The test speed was set at 0.01 mm/s according to empirical values. Axial and lateral displacements were measured by external linear variable differential transducers (LVDT) mounted on two opposite sides of the specimen. The test setup is shown in Figure 5 c). The load was applied into the internal original concrete core. Due to the template used, the confining material was applied with an offset of 10 mm. Eccentricity of the load is minimized by the movable support of the testing machine

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The results of the two test series are shown in Table 3. Compared to the unconfined reference specimens, a strengthening effect could be achieved for all specimens. The respective percentage increase in load-bearing capacity ΔF in relation to the unconfined reference is listed in the table. Remarkable is the increase in load-bearing capacity of 17 % in both series caused only by a 20 mm thick layer of fine-grained concrete. The increase results from the enlargement of the cross-section and the high compressive strength of the fine-grained concrete compared to the core concrete. At the same time, surface preparation by means of sandblasting produced a good bond between the old and new concrete. This led to the increased overall stiffness of the specimen, whereupon a considerable increase in load-bearing capacity could be achieved. This can be useful, for example, for structural components with low reinforcement requirements. By restoring the load-bearing capacity, the old concrete can be repassivated at the same time without significantly increasing the cross-section. Just two layers of carbon fiber textile and a total system thickness of 20 mm can lead to an increase in load-bearing capacity of around 60 %, where, as expected, the effect is more pronounced at lower compressive strengths of the strengthened component. A difference of 8-10 % can be seen between the confined specimen of the two series. The experimental results are tabulated below.

Table 3: Experimental results

Series	Label	Age	H	F _{max}	ΔF	Strength-increase	CoV
-	-	[d]	[cm]	[kN]	[kN]	[%]	[%]
C20	R-1	107	100.7	1125.2	1107.1	0	2.13
	R-2	107	101.0	1115.6			
	R-3	107	100.8	1080.5			
	FC-1	106	100.3	1332.0	1299.7	17	3.70
	FC-2	106	100.4	1322.6			
	FC-2	106	100.4	1244.5			
	2L20-1	104	100.3	1892.4	1847.8	66.9	2.67
	2L20-2	104	100.1	1794.9			
	2L20-3	104	100.4	1856.1			
	4L23-1	110	100.2	2047.8	2099.3	89.6	2.54
4L23-2	110	100.7	2096.1				
4L23-3	110	100.4	2154.1				
C55	R-1	294	100.4	1845.4	1901,1	0	2.7
	R-2	294	100.2	1969.8			
	R-3	294	100.9	1888.2			
	FC-1	302	100.4	2248.8	2227.7	17.2	2.07
	FC-2	302	101.0	2259.6			
	FC-3	302	100.3	2174.8			
	2L20-1	295	100.6	2895.3	2978.1	56.7	7.06
	2L20-2	295	100.4	3216.4			
	2L20-3	295	100.4	2822.7			
	4L20-1	301	100.4	3484.2	3454.5	81.7	1.48
4L20-2	301	99.8	3395.6				
4L20-3	301	100.3	3483.7				

Specimen confined with four layers of carbon fiber textile achieved on average a strength increase of 90 % for the series C20 and 82 % for C55, where some were able to achieve almost double the carrying capacity. The diagrams shown below illustrate the load-displacement progression of each specimen compared to the unconfined reference. It should be mentioned that the values shown here are average values of the strain gages applied on the steel reinforcement, in longitudinal as well as in transverse direction.

Figure 6: Load-Displacement-Diagrams of all experimental results

The diagrams show the average values of two strain gauges applied to the reinforcing steel on opposite sides. Values with a negative sign represent compression in the longitudinal direction, while those with a positive sign represent elongation in the transverse direction.

Typical behavior of RC components confined with TRC can be seen. After reaching and exceeding the core concrete compressive strength, a clear core failure can be observed, which can be observed by the abrupt increase of the transverse strain of the concrete. As microcracking progressed, load transfer occurred from the core concrete to the confining material. The transfer of tensile stresses into the confining layer can be detected by an audible cracking in the confinement shell of the fine-grained concrete. The cracking indicates the formation of a crack pattern in the confining material, whereupon the carbon fiber textile is activated and a renewed load transfer takes place. Accordingly, due to cracking and activation of the passive confinement, the ductility of the component increases.

The failure of the specimen occurs due to a recognizable tensile failure of the carbon fiber textile, which can be seen in Figures 7 and 8. However, due to the internal steel reinforcement, the component does not suddenly fail. A continuous loss of carrying load can be observed with the increase of the crack pattern.

a) b) c) d)
Figure 7: Specimen of the series C20 after testing: a) R; b) FC20; c) 2L20; d) 4L23

a) b) c) d)
Figure 8: Specimen of the series C55 after testing: a) R; b) FC20; c) 2L20; d) 4L20

SUMMARY

In the present paper, a part of a more extensive experimental program is presented. The presented test results show that a moderate increase in the load-bearing capacity can already be achieved with just a 20 mm layer of high-strength fine-grained concrete. However, due to cracking mechanisms, the low tensile strength of the fine-grained concrete and different modulus of elasticity of the concretes, there is no increase in load-bearing capacity proportional to the increase in cross-section. Furthermore, a considerable increase in load-bearing capacity can be achieved with two layers. It is shown, that four layers of carbon fiber textile can also be placed in a 20 mm system. In this way, the load-bearing capacity can be restored or even increased without substantially increasing the cross-section of the component. Increases in load-bearing capacity of up to 90% were achieved with four layers. Even if only slight increases in load-bearing capacity are required in existing structures, the test results show the extraordinary performance of this material.

Additionally, the statement from the literature that the reinforcing effect is greater for components with lower compressive strengths than for those with higher compressive strengths was confirmed by comparing the results of the two series. On average, a difference of approximately 10 % between the series C20 and C55 could be determined.

The load-displacement diagrams also show that the ductility of the confined specimen increases, which can be an additional safety measure in exceptional cases.

TRC offers an innovative solution, especially in terms of material efficiency and sustainability. In addition, due to corrosion resistance, the components can easily survive the life of classic reinforced concrete.

In order to enable the new type of reinforcement to enter the market, a generally applicable and reliable design model must be created based on certain characteristic values relevant to structural engineering. This must cover the design of load-bearing capacity, serviceability, and durability. To this end, the behavior of the composite material under various loading situations must be investigated.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

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